

Dehydration-Dehydrogenation of Isopropyl Alcohol on Pure V_2O_5 and doped with Alkali Metal Oxides

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The catalytic decomposition of isopropyl alcohol (IPA) on pure V_2O_5 and alkali metal oxides doped V_2O_5 has been studied in flow system. The reaction is predominantly dehydration with lower dehydrogenation percentage of IPA. The results reveal that the addition of Li_2O (0.01 mol %) increases the catalytic conversion of IPA and propylene yield relative to untreated V_2O_5 catalyst whereas decreased progressively by increasing the amount of dopant oxide up to 5 mol %. The addition of Na_2O or K_2O retards both activity and selectivity of V_2O_5 , and affects only the sites responsible for alcohol dehydration. The activation energies of the catalysts have been calculated. The role of the dopants that affects the decomposition of IPA is discussed in relation to the position of Fermi energy as well as the defect structure created by doping mechanism.

VANADIUM pentoxide catalysts are widely used in the selective oxidation of many organic compounds. In order to improve its activity and selectivity, transition¹ and alkali² metal oxides are often introduced into its matrix. The development of the catalyst surface by alkali metal introduction has been interpreted according to the variation of the surface acidic sites³. Fikis *et al.*⁴ proposed an elimination-type reaction mechanism for 2-propanol decomposition and a relationship was established between the catalyst activity and the presence of acidic species on the solid surface. Biswas *et al.*⁵ reported the catalytic decomposition of isopropyl alcohol on V_2O_5 doped with lithium. The results showed a contradiction with the view that the dehydration takes place at the acid centers on the surface. On the other hand, several workers⁶ suggested that the dehydration of isopropyl alcohol on semiconductors may as well be examined in terms of their electrical properties. In our earlier work⁷, we concluded that V_2O_5 - Li_2O system differs in its conduction properties from that containing Na_2O or K_2O oxides. Therefore, the first purpose of the present work is to demonstrate how the addition of various amounts of alkali metal oxides affects the catalytic activity and selectivity of V_2O_5 catalysts. The second purpose is to correlate the catalytic activity behaviour with the Fermi energy as well as the changes in the active centers created via the doping mechanism. We have studied the activities and selectivities of pure V_2O_5 and that doped with alkali metal oxides using dehydration-dehydrogenation of isopropyl alcohol (IPA) in flow system. The results have

been correlated with the electrical conductivity and ir spectroscopy.

Experimental

Ammonium metavanadate (AMV) and the alkali metal nitrates (both AnalaR) were used. Unsupported V_2O_5 catalysts were prepared by the calcination of AMV in a muffle furnace in a stream of air at 573–873 K for 2 h. V_2O_5 doped with Li, Na or K oxides was prepared by adding the calculated amounts of their nitrate salts to AMV in ratios ranging from 0.01 to 5% (mol/mol). The salts were admixed using double-distilled water, then evaporated on a water-bath and finally dried in an oven (383 K). The product samples were calcined at 773 K a pure V_2O_5 .

Procedure: The catalytic activities of different prepared catalysts were tested using a conventional flow reactor. Purified air or nitrogen (as carrier gases) were fed with isopropyl alcohol (IPA) vapour into the reactor. The exit feed was analysed chromatographically using a Pye-Unicam gas chromatograph with 20% BEG column coated on celite. Before each run, the catalysts were activated by passing air at 573 K for 4 h. The electrical conductivity measurements were carried out as described by Champan *et al.*⁸ in presence of air flow. Voltage was supplied by Keithley 240 A instrument and the current measured with a Keithley 410 A picoameter. The temperature was controlled with a Gallenkamp thermostat. Ir spectra (KBr) were obtained on a Perkin-Elmer 559 B spectrophotometer.

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Results and Discussion

Ir spectra: The ir spectra of pure V_2O_5 and doped with 5 mol % Li^+ , Na^+ or K^+ calcined at 773 K were recorded in Fig. 1. Curve (a), shows the spectrum of pure V_2O_5 , catalyst shows (curve a)

Fig. 1. Ir spectra for: (a) pure V_2O_5 and promoted with 5 mol % of (b) Li, (c) Na and (d) K.

strong band at 1020 cm^{-1} corresponds to $\nu_{V=O}$ vibration⁹. It is reported¹⁰ that the $V=O$ groups are projected perpendicular to the $V-O-V$ net plan. Hence, the stretching vibration mode of $V=O$ groups can be approximately regarded as independent of the other modes. The band at 825 cm^{-1} belongs ν_{V-O-V} vibration in the lattice layer¹¹. The addition of 5 mol % Li^+ or K^+ into V_2O_5 lattice leads to a significant change in the absorption spectra of the untreated V_2O_5 (curves b and d) whereas no such change was observed in case of V_2O_5 treated with Na^+ (curve c).

Electrical conductivity measurements: The electrical conductivity measurements were carried out to understand the semiconducting properties. The activation energies of carriers of pure V_2O_5 as well as doped with alkali metal ions are obtained. The value of E_a has been calculated using the equation¹²,

$$\sigma = \sigma_0 \exp^{-E_a/RT}$$

where σ is the conductivity and E_a is the activation energy. The variation of the activation energy with the amount of doping is shown in Fig. 2. The results show that among the values of E_a at lower % doping (0.01), only V_2O_5 doped with Li^+ shows an observable decrease. On increasing the dopant concentrations up to 5 mol %, the E_a value increases in case of Li^+ and Na^+ while it decreases

Fig. 2. Plots of activation energy vs (Δ), pure V_2O_5 and % doping with (\bullet) Li , (\circ) Na and (\times) K ions.

in case of K^+ . In the electrical conductivity of vanadium bronzes¹³ it has been found that the lithium atoms enter into V_2O_5 lattice interstitially, giving up its electron to the host lattice, and these electrons are trapped, possibly, at the oxygen defects. Thermal energy excites the electrons from trapping centers forming V^{4+} sites. The conduction then arises due to hopping of electrons from V^{4+} to V^{5+} sites. This hopping mechanism is widely accepted for transport mechanism in the vanadium bronzes¹⁴. In view of Holstein treatment¹⁵ and its reformation by Fridman¹⁶ and Eagle¹⁷, the electronic conduction through polaron and/or hopping, necessitates the simultaneous presence of both sites. However, the decrease in the value of activation energy on addition of 0.01 mol % Li^+ reveals that the conduction increases via the formation of donor and acceptor sites. This may be due to the high degree of Li^+ diffusion into V_2O_5 lattice than that of Na^+ or K^+ ions.

On increasing the percentage of Li^+ dopant, the value of E_a increases, which explains for the increase in Fermi energy while decrease in the catalyst conduction. This is in agreement with the result obtained by Chakrabarty *et al.*⁵. In case of Na^+ or K^+ dopants, the value of activation energy increases in presence of Na^+ ion while it decreases in presence of K^+ . These results may depend on the cross-sectional area of these ions. Consequently, their diffusion rates should play a main role in their conductance behaviour. It is worth noting that the results of activation energy should help us to explain the behaviour of the catalyst activity and selectivity.

Decomposition of isopropyl alcohol (IPA) :

Decomposition of IPA on pure V_2O_5 catalyst : The catalytic activity studies were carried out using unsupported V_2O_5 (100 mg) and IPA (2.2%) vapour in the gas feed. The flow rate of air was 400 ml min^{-1} (STP). Propylene and acetone were found as the major products in the exit feed. The predominant reaction for all the catalysts is dehydration giving water and propylene. Traces

of diisopropyl ether have been detected in the products by carrying out the reaction at lower temperatures.

Effect of calcination temperatures on the V_2O_5 activity towards IPA decomposition: The influence of calcination temperature on the activity and selectivity of V_2O_5 catalyst has been studied and the results are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—CONVERSION, YIELD AND SELECTIVITY OF IPA ON V_2O_5 CATALYST CALCINED AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AT REACTION TEMPERATURE OF 498 K

Calcina- tion temp. K	Conver- sion %	Yield (%)		Selectivity (%)	
		Propylene	Acetone	Propylene	Acetone
573	36.6	30.0	5.9	82.0	16.1
673	63.9	59.5	4.5	92.0	7.0
773	57.1	52.5	4.4	91.9	7.6
873	37.7	31.4	3.1	83.3	8.2

The results indicate an increase in the percentage conversion and yield of propylene on increasing the calcination temperature from 573 to 673 K while a decrease in its values on further calcination upto 873 K. Also, it appears that the lattice dimension has no effect on the catalyst selectivity in the range 673–773 K. The effect of the catalyst porosity on the diffusion of IPA within the cylindrical pores has been investigated¹⁸ using Wheeler treatment¹⁹. The effectiveness factor was calculated and it was found equal unity which indicates that the surface porosity has no effect on the catalytic reaction rate. The calcination temperature of 773 K was chosen for the following experiments because at this temperature V_2O_5 has a well-defined lattice structure and a high selectivity.

Effect of the reaction temperature on the decomposition products of IPA on V_2O_5 catalyst: The effect of different catalytic reaction temperatures on the dehydration-dehydrogenation processes on V_2O_5 catalyst calcined at 773 K has been carried out and the results are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—CONVERSION, YIELD AND SELECTIVITY OF IPA ON V_2O_5 CATALYST CALCINED AT 773 K AT DIFFERENT REACTION TEMPERATURES

Reaction temp. K	Conversion %	Yield (%)		Selectivity (%)	
		Propylene	Acetone	Propylene	Acetone
423	13.9	10.5	2.2	75.6	15.8
473	49.7	45.3	3.9	90.2	7.9
498	57.1	52.5	4.4	91.9	7.6
523	90.0	83.1	5.7	92.3	5.9
573	98.4	69.1	5.8	70.2	5.9
623	100.0	60.5	5.8	60.5	5.8

The results show that the percentage conversion increases sharply at the reaction temperature range 423–523 K while it attains 100% at 623 K with lower yield and selectivity of propylene. Also, the dehydration reaction is predominant rather than dehydrogenation as predicted from the high yield of propylene. On the other hand, the variation of acetone yield with the reaction temperature was found almost constant in the range 523–623 K. These results explain that the sites responsible for dehydration are activated whereas the sites responsible for dehydrogenation are not affected on increasing the reaction temperature.

Effect of carrier gas on the decomposition products of IPA on V_2O_5 catalyst: The kinetic studies on the decomposition of IPA over V_2O_5 calcined at 773 K have been carried out at 523 K using air and nitrogen as carrier gases. The variation of percentage conversion, yield and selectivity with the reaction time are shown in Figs. 3 and 4. In case of IPA+air (Fig. 3), the percentage conversions of IPA and propylene yield are increased very fast at the beginning of reaction and the steady state is reached after 1 h. The yield and selectivity of acetone have low and constant values on increasing the reaction time. These data demonstrate that V_2O_5 is a very active catalyst to the decomposition of IPA in presence of air and no decay is observed in its activity and selectivity on increasing the reaction time. This means that V_2O_5 is dominant phase during IPA decomposition reaction²⁰.

Fig. 3. Plots of activity of pure V_2O_5 vs reaction time at reaction temperature of 523 K in presence of air as a carrier: (O) % conversion, (●) % yield of propylene, (●) % selectivity of propylene, (x) % yield of acetone and (Δ) % selectivity of acetone.

It is known that the rate-limiting step with the vanadia catalysts is the reduction of the oxygen

Fig. 4. Plots of activity of pure V_2O_5 vs reaction time at reaction temperature of 523 K in presence of N_2 gas as a carrier: (O) % conversion, (●) % yield of propylene, (x) % yield of acetone and (Δ) % selectivity of acetone.

gas^{21,22}, and at the same time the reduced catalyst will be most effective. However, when IPA is adsorbed on the catalyst surface, electrons are donated to V^{5+}/V^{4+} bands²¹ (IPA reduces V^{5+} to V^{4+}) and the energy gap decreases while the electrical conductance increases¹⁸. Hence, the catalyst surface in the presence of (IPA+air) probably adsorbs O_2 gas while the ratio of V^{4+}/V^{5+} should hardly change²³ during the catalyst reaction,

This may explain why the activity and selectivity of V_2O_5 catalyst in presence of air do not change with the reaction time.

In case of IPA+ N_2 , we used the same conditions mentioned above. Fig. 4 shows a continuous decrease in the percentage conversion and propylene yield with increasing reaction time. On the other hand, the acetone yield is nearly constant after 20 min, but its values are higher than those obtained in presence of air as carrier. In addition, the steady state needs a long time to attain. The continuous decrease in both catalyst activity and selectivity on increasing the reaction time may be attributed to the decrease in the number of active centers responsible for dehydration process via the evolution of oxygen gas. The following equations may explain the reduction of active centers on exposure to IPA in presence of N_2 gas,

It is worth mentioning that a stable black color was observed for V_2O_5 catalyst after exposure to IPA in the presence of N_2 gas which is characteristics of lower valence of vanadium oxides.

Fig. 5. IR spectra for pure V_2O_5 after exposed to IPA in presence of (b) air as carrier and (c) N_2 as a carrier at the reaction temperature of 523 K, and (a) pure V_2O_5 without reaction with IPA for comparison.

Furthermore, in the reduced catalyst investigation by IR absorption spectra (Fig. 5), curve (c) shows an observable change in the spectrum of V_2O_5 in the range 1000–600 cm^{-1} when the reaction of IPA occurred in presence of N_2 gas. On the other hand, no change occurs in the absorption bands of V_2O_5 when the reaction takes place in presence of air as indicated in curve (b). Curve (a) presents the absorption bands of pure V_2O_5 (without reaction of IPA) for comparison. The prediction of lower oxides of vanadium (V_2O_3) is found in agreement with the reported results²⁴.

The catalytic decomposition of IPA on V_2O_5 doped with alkali metal oxides: The catalytic decomposition of IPA over V_2O_5 doped with Li^+ , Na^+ or K^+ in the range 0.01–5 mol % calcined at 773 K for 2 h was carried out using the same experimental conditions mentioned above. The results are shown in Figs. 6–8.

In case of Li-dopant (Fig. 6), the lower additive (0.01) increases the activity (% conversion) as well as the yield of propylene compared to undoped V_2O_5 catalyst. On increasing the dopant concentration, a continuous decrease in both percentage conversion and the propylene yield upto 5 mol %. The presence of lower concentration from Li^+ into V_2O_5 lattice increases the number of V^{4+} sites²⁵ and consequently, increases the catalyst activity¹³. Furthermore, the decrease in the Fermi energy as indicated in Fig. 2 should

Fig. 6. Plots of V_2O_5 doped with Li vs Li concentration at reaction temperature of 498 K: (○) % conversion, (●) % yield of propylene, (●) % selectivity of propylene, (×) % yield of acetone and (△) % selectivity of acetone.

Fig. 7. Plots of activity of V_2O_5 doped with Na ions vs Na concentration at reaction temperature of 498 K: (○) % conversion, (●) % yield of propylene, (●) % selectivity of propylene, (×) % yield of acetone and (△) % selectivity of acetone.

enhance the reaction between IPA and the catalyst surface. The decrease in the catalyst activity on increasing the concentration of Li^+ may be attributed to the drastic reduction in dehydration sites. These results are in agreement with the results obtained by Chakrabarty *et al.*⁵. Kimoto and Morrison²⁰ suggested that when the Fermi energy is too low, the selectivity should be poor. On the other hand, if the Fermi energy becomes too high, the selectivity should drop. Therefore,

if the optimum Fermi energy is reached, the selectivity should be improved and the activity should be high.

Fig. 8. Plots of activity of V_2O_5 doped with K ions vs K concentration at reaction temperature of 498 K: (○) % conversion, (●) % yield of propylene, (●) % selectivity of propylene, (×) % yield of acetone and (△) % selectivity of acetone.

In case of V_2O_5 doped with Na^+ or K^+ (Figs. 7 and 8), it appears that the percentage conversion and propylene yield of the catalysts are reduced compared to pure V_2O_5 or doped with Li^+ , while the acetone yield is almost constant in case of K^+ dopant and little increased in case of Na^+ -dopant. This may be attributed to the little diffusion of these ions through V_2O_5 lattice and it may be present as a separate phases on the V_2O_5 surface. Several workers²⁷ reported that the dehydration of alcohols over alumina catalysts was retarded by poisoning of the catalyst surface with sodium or potassium ions. This is due to the decrease in the number of the active surface centers.

In previous study⁷, we concluded that in spite of the fact that the additives of alkali metal ions are monovalent ions, Li^+ gave higher conductivity. Adopting the incorporation mechanism of the monovalent ions, it was found that the charge carrier increases as,

where M is the alkali metal ion, $M|V|''$ represents an alkali metal ion substituted for lattice vanadium and $|e|'$ is a defect electron. The Li^+ diffusion may create more charge carriers by oxygen evolution according to the equation,

where $V|V|'$ are V^{4+} ions replace V^{5+} in its normal position. The evolution of lattice oxygen is accompanied by the reduction of V^{5+} to V^{4+} and consequently, the catalytic activity should improve.

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